

One CGIAR Consultation Workshop on 'Digital Innovation and Transformation in Food-Water-Land Systems in India'

Authors

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Workshop date

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Location

Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India

The CGIAR Digital Innovation Initiative accelerates the transformation towards sustainable and inclusive agrifood systems by generating research-based evidence and innovative digital solutions. It is one of 32 initiatives of CGIAR, a global research partnership for a food-secure future, dedicated to transforming food, land, and water systems in a climate crisis.

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Background

Under its new research for development (R4D) initiative on digital innovation and transformation, the Consultative Group on International Agriculture Research (CGIAR), organised a two-day workshop on 8 and 9 November 2022, at Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India. The workshop was aimed to better understand the actor landscape of the digital ecosystem in food-water-land systems. This includes: the availability, accessibility, gender responsiveness and effectiveness of services; the challenges and opportunities in promoting an inclusive, gender-intentional and beneficial digital ecosystem; and the data management challenges associated with data security and governance. Essential stakeholders encompassing representatives from government, research, private, producer and Non-Governmental Organizations having expertise and experience in digital innovations participated in the workshop (refer to list of participants in Annexure 1).

Purpose of the consultation workshop

The purpose of this consultation was to understand the actor landscape in the digital food-water-land ecosystem, the services they provide, gender-responsiveness of these services, the challenges and opportunities in promoting an inclusive, gender-intentional and beneficial digital ecosystem, and the data management challenges associated with data security and governance. A rapid assessment of the capacity needs of the digital ecosystem actors to address the gender digital divide in their respective domains will also be conducted. The specific objectives of the consultation workshop included:

1. To map the digital ecosystem of food, land and water systems in focus states in India

- a. Identify the various actors involved in the digital ecosystems in Bihar, Odisha and Telangana states of India

- b. Define the regulatory support system that influences the digital ecosystem and limitations, gaps and opportunities associated
- c. Identify user data that is currently available or being collected by the actors - including gender disaggregated secondary data and gaps, if any
- d. Identify how data is currently being managed and used by the actors and the associated security and ethics challenges
- e. Challenges and opportunities faced by the actors for inclusion of potential and unreached users; awareness, penetration, infrastructure, and connectivity challenges faced by them
- f. Identify concrete local partnership opportunities to co-develop innovative digital solutions or fill existing gaps in the local digital innovation ecosystem

2. Capacity Needs assessment of institutional stakeholders and service providers to be able to promote gender digital inclusion.

All insights and nuances that emanated from the discussions during each session are described briefly below. The agenda and detailed program of the workshop is attached in Annexure 2.

Sessions

Introduction to the One CGIAR Initiative on Digital Innovations

In this introductory session, Dr Jawoo Koo (IFPRI), Dr Hom Gartaula (CIMMYT), and Dr Andrea Gardeazabal Monsalve (CIMMYT) – all from One CGIAR – set the tone for the workshop with an overview of the One CGIAR Digital Innovations Initiative. They briefly described the potential of the digital innovations to transform the agri-food systems in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), the prevalence or persistence of the digital divide within geographies, communities and within households, and the challenges that need to be overcome for bridging the digital divide.

The five major work packages (WPs) of the digital innovations initiative include: an enabling environment, digital inclusion, systems modelling, real-time monitoring, and platforms and services (Figure 1). These were all discussed. Dr Jawoo Koo stressed on the importance of co-ordinated activities across these five WPs to deliver a suite of outputs through three pathways (policy, innovation, and capacity building) to support three levels (decision-makers, service providers, and users).

The expected outcomes from the One CGIAR digital innovations initiative were also discussed as follows:

- Informed policymakers and investors formulate enabling policies for locally-led digital ecosystems, develop digital strategies, establish public-private partnerships, and attract strategic investments toward bridging the digital divide;
- Improved digital services and information systems provide more timely, accurate, and actionable information that helps agri-food system actors manage climate and food security risks; and
- Empowered women and youth use digital technologies, leading to improved livelihoods and job opportunities.

Figure 1. Five Work Packages of the One CGIAR- Digital Initiative

Thereafter, Dr Gartaula elaborated on the topic of gender digital divide in India. He briefly explained the barriers to women’s participation in digitized agri-food value chains, such as, social norms, lack of access and control over resources, and lack of digital inclusion. He also described the immediate and long-term opportunities for inclusive digital innovations, by

forging partnership with non-traditional actors (women, youth and marginal communities). For all the subsequent sessions participants were divided into groups, for more discussions on these topics where the participants could share their insights, opinions and expertise.

Mapping the Digital Ecosystems

The major aspects discussed during the breakout sessions included the existing digital infrastructure in agri-food systems; the key actors involved, the types of services provided by these actors; and mode of service delivery. The digital ecosystem is huge and there is a need to investigate micro ecosystems so as to facilitate mapping.

The existing infrastructure includes mobile-based apps, Web-based Apps, Internet of Things (IoT), MIS, GIS modelling, Geo tagging, etc., to name a few. Though digital infrastructure exists, it is inadequate, especially in the rural areas due to poor connectivity (bandwidth) and low accessibility to mobile devices among and within rural households. There are multiple actors, providing different digital innovative services, using multiple service delivery methods.

The major actors include government institutions (Central, State and Regional), private sector stakeholders, NGOs, research organizations, farmers, entrepreneurs, Farmer Producer Organizations (FPOs), Self-Help Groups (SHGs), financial institutions, knowledge intermediaries, etc. The major services being provided include crop advisory and information services, supply chain management services, market information, market linkage, facilitation services, financial inclusion, weather advisory, technical services (software development, web management), etc.

The main mode of service delivery is through mobile phones (WhatsApp, SMS, IVR), Internet of Things, etc., mostly facilitated by human intermediaries such as extension agents, staff of Common Service centres (CSCs), staff/members of the Agricultural Production Committees/Clusters (APCs), SHGs, FPOs, Village Champions and Village Youth.

Laying the Foundation for Inclusive Digital Innovations

Opportunities and challenges in promoting inclusive, gender-intentional and beneficial digital ecosystem were discussed during this session. One of the major challenges cited by the participants is lack of availability of sex disaggregated data, even with respect to ownership and usage of digital tools (such as mobile phones), while designing digital solutions. Some actors opined that gender is not well-defined even from the government perspective, for instance in the census data itself gender is not given due weightage. Another crucial challenge identified is the lack of capacity to assess the needs of women and other marginalized and vulnerable groups.

Digital services are designed and delivered mostly in a supply driven (PUSH) and top-down approach. The contents pushed through these services are mostly not need based and are not context specific. Gender and social inclusion is an afterthought once the digital service has been designed and deployed. Need assessment, along with community engagement, during the process of designing digital innovations is an important aspect to be considered before deploying digital services. Technical service providers view gender inclusion as a

lesser challenge in the project design phase itself even if the gender component is included, but most of the institutes do not investigate this aspect in the project design phase.

Some participants opined that currently accessibility is not a problem but the hitch is lack of need-based digital services. Affordability, information gap, and lack of incentives are some of the other challenges identified by the participants. Some of the participants felt that these services would be more used if they were bundled with enhanced market access, and also enabled sale of surplus produce, supported farmers in obtaining better rates for their produce, etc. They also felt that there is a huge opportunity for digital service penetration through mobilisation of women into groups. Digital innovations have wide scope in facilitating access to credit and empowering women and other marginalised groups, financially as well as socially. Other major opportunities for making digital innovations inclusive and gender intentional are bundling up services, using a combination of technologies, delivering services with human facilitation and integrating the gender component into the government's monitoring and evaluation system. This will enhance collection of gender disaggregated data and tap into the potential of rural youth in digital service delivery by augmenting their capacity as they are more trusted and have more access to digital technologies in rural areas.

Data, Evidence and Responsible Digital Innovations

In this session participants discussed what kinds of data are available and collected, how it is collected, is it gender disaggregated, what are the data gaps, data security and management challenges; and what are the efforts that can improve and address data challenges. A wide variety of data is collected according to the purpose, such as primary, secondary, spatial, non-spatial, qualitative, quantitative, caste-class-sex disaggregated, crowd sourced data (to train the digital application), etc. Data is collected both digitally (web-based Apps, QR codes, MIS based Apps) and non-digitally. Some NGOs and private sector institutions are providing digital tools, such as tablets, to the enumerators while others are collecting through paper-based tools, such as questionnaires and interview schedules. Mostly data is enumerated in the field by agencies, agents, village resource persons or village level champions and local youth, who are given orientation and trained prior to data collection. There was a consensus among the participants that gender disaggregated data is not collected, unless specified in the project design and linked to a mandate.

The unanimously identified challenge is lack of quality in the data as well as access to it. Often, the inherent gender bias of the enumerators or data collectors, despite training and orientation, raises questions on the credibility of the primary data and thereby as a source of secondary data as well. Also, data collection is done at various levels, such as at individual level, household level, village level, field level, community level, as well as national and sub-national levels.

This brings to mind the issue of non-standardized data. The data quality itself is intersectional as observed by various participants; for example, data quality significantly varies between men and women or between castes or classes. Participants agreed that there is need for data sharing between stakeholders. However, there are existing gaps in practice not only due to lack of trust between various stakeholders, but also due to lack of knowledge on who has what type of data. Access to data in a scenario where multiple stakeholders are involved in a single initiative is problematic and at times the data from stakeholders at various levels don't match. Also, sometimes, the field level data and the reported data have wide gaps, such as beneficiaries listed under different schemes. This

creates data silos that prevent stakeholders from coming together and sharing data that could have been pooled across multiple actors and platforms. All these forces different stakeholders from various sectors to start from scratch while working on digital initiatives, although data is available in the digital ecosystem. Mechanisms to facilitate data sharing are needed to operationalize the format in which the data is stored to make it compatible to the needs and capacities of all the relevant stakeholders.

Lack of a strong privacy policy in the digital apps developed was also identified as a major hindrance to going forward in an increasingly digital era. It is exacerbated by the fact that most of the apps have privacy policies in English rather than in the native/vernacular language spoken by the farmers. Lack of capacity to manage and analyse the big data produced in the digital ecosystem is another challenge pointed out by the participants. There is a wide gap in making use of this data that already exists, which can be seen as legacy data, to formulate further effective strategies for digital innovations.

Some of the measures to address these challenges as shared by the participants are creation of a common dashboard or interface for accessing and sharing the data with an option to question the data as well, so that need-specific data can be accessed and matters of interoperability can also be solved. There is a need to set up a convergence platform because ultimately various stakeholders with similar service models reach farmers with the same queries, but for different platforms, challenging the availability of systematic and organized data. Ethical practices should be adhered to, such as agreements between the various stakeholders including farmers, while sharing the data so as to build trust between stakeholders as well as for data security.

Participants believe that government institutions are still hesitant to share data. If the data is opened up for analysis, more customized and relevant digital services can be delivered. Some of the strategies to solve challenges related to data privacy, as discussed, are storing data in password protected websites, coding of primary data, masking data partially, having

data privacy policy and user level agreements (ULA), accessing and storing data through sensors. Engaging third party evaluators (external agency, research institutes) to assess data quality and impact of the project is another strategy that is being already practiced by some stakeholders.

Strategic Partnerships and Capacity Needs Assessment to Promote Gender Digital Inclusion

In this session, aspects related to current patterns of collaboration in digital service delivery, the types of partnerships that are needed for promoting digitally inclusive innovation and the existing capacity needs and gaps to enable gender-responsive and inclusive digital innovations were discussed. All the participants acknowledged that partnerships with multiple stakeholders are crucial for providing innovative digital solutions. There is general agreement that most of the digital initiatives are project based, and therefore further scaling up calls for much support from government, especially for a strong partnership. This was further validated by quoting the success of Jeevika Project from Bihar. Partnerships are done mainly for knowledge sharing (research organizations), technical capacity building

(private sector, NGOs), data collection (NGOs), service delivery (NGOs, private sector, government organizations), feedback and impact assessment (NGOs, private sector, research organizations), evidence building (research organizations), handholding/service expansion (government sector). Other interesting aspects discussed were the need for partnerships to have a shared vision, flexible/adaptive framework, strong governance as well as facilitators, such as innovation brokers, so that it is sustainable, scalable and cross learning can take place. Actor landscape mapping is another measure that can expedite partnerships as advocated by some other stakeholders.

The main points to address the capacity gaps and enable gender-responsive digital innovations are discussed now. Gender is mostly an afterthought in most initiatives. Internalizing the concept of gender and harmonising efforts while focussing on the gender dimension is crucial but, it is also a challenge as observed by the stakeholders. There is still a lack of awareness on why gender matters in agriculture and agricultural projects. Hence, there is a need to sensitise multiple stakeholders (individuals and also at the organisational level) on bringing gender inclusion within the ambits of the digital projects and programmes

they are involved with. To start with, digital initiatives should have a clear intention to be gender inclusive and have identified action points/nodes for acting on it. To enable this whole process there must be a continuous effort on capacity development at all levels through a gender lens. Generally, digital tools do not have a women centric design, and for this, trans-disciplinary partnerships need to be nurtured in the developmental phase. The importance of having a gender focal point wherein gender inclusiveness is ensured and incentivized was also discussed. Some of the stakeholders shared good practices, such as identifying gender champions in a group who will act as influencers and ensure gender inclusiveness. Another good practice championed was to include women and other marginalised groups while pilot testing digital innovations so as to ensure a gender inclusive design and promote gender conscious scaling. Some also felt that collecting evidence from gender inclusive practices and sharing it with stakeholders could also be one of the strategies for promoting gender inclusion across a wider expanse of stakeholders.

Annexure 1

Table 1: List of Participants

S.No	Name of Participant	Organization	Designation	Email/Contact
1	Ronali Pradhan	Digital Green	Regional Head- Odisha	ronali@digitalgreen.org
2	Dinesh Chauhan	DeHaat	Vice President - NewInitiatives	dinesh.chauhan@agrevolution.in
3	Dibyakanta Nayak	Reliance Foundation	State Coordinator Information Services -Odisha	Dibyakanta.Nayak@reliancefoundation.org
4	Om Routray	Sourcetrace	VP Marketing	om@sourcetrace.com
5	Vijayasekaran Duraisamy	Sourcetrace	Head, RemoteSensing	vijayasekaran@sourcetrace.com
6	Navin Bhushan	Microsave Consulting	Project Director	navin.bhushan@microsave.net
7	Nikki Pilania Chaudhary	Mango Dairies	Founder	chaudharyfarms@gmail.com
8	Rajesh Chundi	Gloqal Inc	President and CEO	chundirr@gloqalinc.com
9	Luna Panda	Pragati, Koraput	Executive Director	luna@pragatikoraput.org
10	Prabhakar Adhikari	Pragati, Koraput	Secretary	pragatikoraput@gmail.com
11	Sarbanib Bose	Pradan	Executive (Projects)	sarbanibose@pradan.net
12	Surjit Behera	Pradan	Project Coordinator	surjitbehera@pradan.net
13	Prabhat Kumar	SumArth	President	prabhat@microxfoundation.com
14	Utkarsh Vijay	Samagra	Lead, KONNECT Team	utkarsh@samagravernance.in
15	Morup Namgail	IKSL (IFFCO Kisan)	Head, Agritech Development	morup.namgail@iffco kisan.com
16	K K Singh	IMD (Meghdoot)	Scientist and Head, AASD, IMD	kksingh2022@gmail.com

17	Sarvanan Raj	National Institute of Agricultural Extension Management (MANAGE)	Director, Agriculture Extension	saravananraj@hotmail.com
18	Navesh Kumar Pattanayak	ADAPT	AAO	navesh2007@gmail.com
19	P.J. Mishra	OUAT	Dean Extension Education	deanextensionouat@yahoo.com
20	Sheetal Sharma	IRRI	Scientist- Soil Science and Research Leader - Digital Tools and Big Data, IRRI (WP5)	sheetal.sharma@irri.org
21	Ranjitha Puskur	IRRI	Country Representative for India, and Research Leader - Gender and Livelihoods, IRRI (WP2)	r.puskur@irri.org
22	Hom Gartaula	CIMMYT	Scientist- Gender and Social Inclusion Specialist, CIMMYT (WP2)	H.GARTAULA@cgiar.org
23	Niyati Singaraju	IRRI	Postdoctoral Fellow - Gender Research, IRRI (WP2)	n.singaraju@irri.org
24	Jawoo Koo	IFPRI	Senior Research Fellow, IFPRI	j.koo@cgiar.org
25	Andrea Gardeazabal Monsalve	CIMMYT	MEL Manager - ICT for agriculture	A.GARDEAZABAL@cgiar.org

26	Renaud Mathieu	IRRI	Senior Scientist I - Geospatial Science	r.mathieu@irri.org
27	Mukund Variar	IRRI	State Coordinator,IRRI, Odisha	m.variar@irri.org
28	Preeti Bharti	IRRI	Associate Scientist,IRRI	p.bharti@irri.org
29	Ajay Kumar Mishra	IRRI	Associate Scientist, IRRI	a.k.mishra@irri.org
30	Deepak Sethi	IRRI	Consultant, IRRI	Desethi86@gmail.com
31	Shakti Prakash Nayak	IRRI	Knowledge Management Specialist, IRRI	s.p.nayak@irri.org
32	Nimisha Mittal	Centre for Research on Innovation and Science Policy (CRISP)	Lead Researcher	nimisha61@gmail.com
33	Ditty Maria Dominic	CRISP	Research Fellow	ditty794@gmail.com
34	Rengalakshmi R	MS Swaminathan Research Foundation (MSSRF)	Director - Ecotechnology	rengalakshmi@mssrf.res.in
35	Rabindra Behera	MS Swaminathan Research Foundation (MSSRF)	Coordinator - Project RESILIENCE	rabindrabehera@mssrf.res.in
36	Gopal Krishna	ICRAF	Geoinformatics DataScientist	G.Krishna@cgiar.org
37	Prasun Gangopadhyay	BISA	Lead, Digital Agriculture	p.gangopadhyay@cgiar.org
38	Satish Nagaraji	ICRISAT	Senior Manager, Digital Agriculture	s.nagaraji@cgiar.org

39	Aparajita Kujur	IRRI	Senior Specialist- Communications	aparajita.kujur@irri.org
40	Dayam Khan	IRRI	IT	d.khan@irri.org
41	Santosh Rao	IRRI	Assistant Manager- Finance and Administration, IRRI	s.s.rao@irri.org

Annexure 2

Workshop Agenda

DAY 1, November 8, 2022		
INAUGURAL SESSION		
09.30 - 09.40	Welcome and Introduction to the stakeholder consultation workshop	Dr Sheetal Sharma
09.40 - 10.10	Introduction of participants	Ms Aparajita Kujur
10.10 - 10.30	Introduction to the CGIAR Initiative on Digital Innovation	Dr Jawoo Koo
10.30 - 10.40	Group Photo	Mr Santosh Rao
10.40 - 11.00	<i>High Tea</i>	
TECHNICAL SESSION I: Mapping Digital Ecosystem		
11.00 - 11.20	Overview of the digital ecosystem in food, water, and land systems in India with a focus on reasons for exclusion, opportunities, and constraints for closing the digital divide	Dr Hom Gartaula
11.20 - 12.20	<p>Breakout session</p> <p>Mapping the digital ecosystems</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the existing digital infrastructure in agri-food systems in the regions you operate? • Who are the key actors? – (Is it mostly the private sector or government sector operating?) • What kind of services do the majority of providers engage in? (Advisory and information services, market linkages, financial access, supply chain management, artificial intelligence, etc.?) • What mode of service delivery is most common? (mobile phones, internet of things, sms, etc.) 	<p>Group 1</p> <p>Facilitator: Jawoo Koo Rapporteur: Shakti & Deepak</p> <p>Group 2</p> <p>Facilitator: Andrea Rapporteur: Niyati & Ajay</p> <p>Group 3</p> <p>Facilitator: Hom Rapporteur: Preeti</p>

12.20 - 12.50	Break out Group presentations	3 groups 10 minutes each
12.50 - 13.00	Wrap up of Session II Brief overview of Session III	Dr Hom Gartaula
13.00 - 14.00	<i>Lunch</i>	
SESSION II: Laying the Foundation for Inclusive Digital Innovations		
14.00 - 15.30	<p>Opportunities and challenges faced by the respective stakeholders for promoting inclusive digital innovations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the opportunities in promoting an inclusive, and gender-intentional, beneficial digital ecosystem? • What are the challenges associated in promoting such a system? (Logistics, scale of investment, data availability, etc.) • What efforts according to you can promote an inclusive digital ecosystem? • What collaborative research opportunities can we develop to improve gender-responsiveness in the services? 	<p>Group 1</p> <p>Facilitator: Jawoo Rapporteur: Shakti & Deepak</p> <p>Group 2</p> <p>Facilitator: Andrea Rapporteur: Niyati & Ajay</p> <p>Group 3</p> <p>Facilitator: Hom Rapporteur: Preeti</p>
15.30 - 15.50	<i>Tea break</i>	
15.50 - 16.20	Breakout group presentations - Session II	10 minutes/group
16.20 - 17.00	Day 1 Wrap up and reflections	Dr Andrea Gardeazabal Monsalve
17.00 onwards	<i>Cocktails & Mocktails</i>	

DAY 2, November 9, 2022		
TECHNICAL SESSION III: Data and Evidence and Responsible Digital Innovations		
09.00 - 09.15	Introduction to the session	Dr Andrea Gardeazabal Monsalve
09.15 - 10.30	Breakout session <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current systems of data production and use by various actors - what, who, how? Data management including data security and ethics • What kind of data is available for designing and service provision? • How do they collect the data? Is it gender- disaggregated? • What kind of data gaps – timeliness, adequacy? • What are the major data security and management challenges you face? • What efforts can improve and address the data challenges? 	Group 1 Facilitator: Jawoo Rapporteur: Ajay Group 2 Facilitator: Sheetal Rapporteur: Niyati Group 3 Facilitator: Andrea Rapporteur: Preeti Group 4 Facilitator: Hom Rapporteur: Shakti
10.30 - 11.00	<i>Tea/Coffee Break</i>	
11.00 - 11.40	Breakout group presentations	Each group (10 minutes)
11.40 - 12.00	Insights from the session: wrapup	Dr Andrea Gardeazabal Monsalve

TECHNICAL SESSION IV: Strategic Partnerships		
12.00 - 12.05	Introduction to the session	Dr Sheetal Sharma
12.05 - 13.00	<p>Breakout session</p> <p>Partnerships and networks to promote inclusive, responsible and gender- intentional digital innovations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What partners and networks are they connected to right now to provide digital services? • What kind of partners and networks do they want to work with to promote inclusive digital services? 	<p>Group 1</p> <p>Facilitator: Jawoo Rapporteur: Ajay</p> <p>Group 2</p> <p>Facilitator: Sheeta Rapporteur: Niyati</p> <p>Group 3</p> <p>Facilitator: Andrea Rapporteur: Preeti</p> <p>Group 4</p> <p>Facilitator: Hom Rapporteur: Shakti</p>
12.00 - 12.05	Introduction to the session	Dr Sheetal Sharma
13.00 - 14.00	<i>Lunch</i>	

TECHNICAL SESSION V: Capacity Needs Assessment to Promote Gender Digital Inclusion		
14.00 - 15.00	<p>Breakout Session</p> <p>Capacity gaps and needs to enable gender responsive and socially inclusive digital ecosystem and innovations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the problems/challenges you face in service provision? • What is your existing capacity to provide services? • What can we put together to improve capacities for providing inclusive digital services and improve diversity in end users? 	<p>Group 1</p> <p>Facilitator: Jawoo Rapporteur: Ajay</p> <p>Group 2</p> <p>Facilitator: Sheetal Rapporteur: Niyati</p> <p>Group 3</p> <p>Facilitator: Andrea Rapporteur: Preeti</p> <p>Group 4</p> <p>Facilitator: Hom Rapporteur: Shakti</p>
15.00 - 15.40	Breakout group presentations	10 minutes per group
15.40 - 16.00	<i>Tea Break</i>	
CLOSING SESSION		
16.00 - 16.15	Closing Remarks- Dr Arabinda Padhee, Principal Secretary, Department of Agriculture and Farmers Empowerment, Government of Odisha	Facilitator: Dr Ranjitha Puskur
16.15 - 16.45	Reflections from the Workshop	Dr Ranjitha Puskur
16.45 - 17.00	Vote of thanks and Wrap up	Dr Sheetal Sharma

Day 1. Three breakout groups

S.No	Group I	Group II	Group III
1	Om Routray (Sourcetrace)	Dinesh Chauhan (DeHaat)	Ronali Pradhan (Digital Green)
2	Navin Bhushan (Microsave Consulting)	Vijaysekaran Duraisamy (Sourcetrace)	Dibyakanta Nayak (Reliance Foundation)
3	Rajesh Chundi (Gloqal Inc)	Nikki Pilonia Chaudhary (Mango Dairies)	Luna Panda (Pragati Koraput)
4	Prabhat Kumar (SumArth)	Sarbani Bose (Pradan)	Prabhakar Adhikari (Pragati Koraput)
5	Morup Namgail (IKSL IFFCO Kisan)	Utkarsh Vijay (Samagra)	Surjit Behera (Pradan)
6	Saravanan Raj (National Institute of Agricultural Extension Management (MANAGE))	KK Singh (IMD Meghdoot)	Navesh Kumar Pattanayak (ADAPT)
7	Ditty Maria Dominic (CRISP)	Nimisha Mittal (CRISP)	P.J. Mishra (OUAT)
8	Rengalakshmi R (MS Swaminathan Research Foundation (MSSRF))	Gopal Krishna (ICRAF)	Rabindra Behera (MS Swaminathan Research Foundation (MSSRF))

9	Satish Nagaraji (ICRISAT)	Prasun Gangopadhyay (BISA)	
10	Jawoo Koo (IFPRI)-Facilitator	Andrea (CIMMYT) - Facilitator	Mukund Variar (IRRI)
11	Sheetal Sharma (IRRI)	Niyati Singaraju (IRRI) - Rapporteur	Hom Gartaula (CIMMYT) - Facilitator
12	Deepak (IRRI)	Renaud (IRRI)	Ranjitha Puskur (IRRI)
13	Shakti (IRRI) - Rapporteur	Ajay (IRRI) - Rapporteur	Preeti (IRRI) - Rapporteur

Four breakout groups for Day 2

S.No	PRIVATE	GOVERNMENT	NGO	RESEARCH ORGANIZATION
1	Ronali Pradhan (Digital Green)	Morup Namgail (IKSL)	Luna Panda (Pragati)	Nimisha Mittal (CRISP)
2	Dinesh Chauhan (DeHaat)	KK Singh (IMD)	Prabhakar Adhikari (Pragati)	Ditty Maria Dominic (CRISP)
3	Dibyakanta Nayak (Reliance Foundation)	Sarvanan Raj (MANAGE)	Sarbani Bose (Pradan)	Rengalakshmi R (MSSRF)
4	Om Routray (SourceTrace)	Navesh Kumar Pattanayak (ADAPT)	Surjit Behera (Pradan)	Rabindra Behera (MSSRF)
5	Vijayasekaran Duraismy (SourceTrace)	P.J. Mishra (OUAT)	Prabhat Kumar (SumArth)	Gopal Krishna (ICRAF)
6	Navin Bhushan (Microsave Consulting)	Sheetal Sharma (IRRI) - Facilitator	Utkarsh Vijay (Samagra)	Prasun Gangopadhyay (BISA)
7	Nikki Pilania Chaudhary (Mago Diaries)	Niyati Singaraju (Rapporteur)	Andrea (Facilitator)	Satish Nagaraji (ICRISAT)
8	Rajesh Chundi (Gloqal Inc)	Deepak (IRRI)	Preeti (Rapporteur)	Hom (Facilitator)
9	Jawoo Koo (IFPRI) - Facilitator	Dr Mukund Variar (IRRI)	Ranjitha Puskur	Shakti (Rapporteur)
10	Ajay (IRRI) - Rapporteur			
11	Renaud (IRRI)			